

VALIDATED FINITE ELEMENT SIMULATION OF POROUS TITANIUM SAMPLES UNDER FATIGUE LOADING FOR DESIGN OPTIMIZATION

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Introduction

Porous titanium scaffolds exhibit elastic properties close to that of bone, and they can promote osseointegration. These features render their use as medical implants attractive. Dental implants represent one of the potential applications of this structure type [1]. Nevertheless, it must be ensured that the porous structure of these implants possess sufficient mechanical stability under fatigue loading occurring in cyclic masticatory loads. Adopting a trial-and-error design optimization strategy using experimental fatigue testing can become costly and time-intensive [2]. This study aims developing and experimentally validating a finite element (FE) simulation approach to predict the fatigue failure of different porous geometries to be used in design optimization.

Methods

Custom cylindrical samples featuring a hemispherical head and incorporating a porous scaffold section in the middle were designed for this study (Fig 1) using. Two porous designs utilizing the Schwarz primitive (SP) and the Schwarz W (SW) cell geometries were compared (Fig 2). Scaffold porosity of 60% and a strut thickness of 200 μm was used for both designs. The samples were additively manufactured (AM) by selective laser melting (SLM) of Ti6Al4V powder. Cyclic mechanical testing to fatigue failure was performed in a combined bending-compression loading mode at 30° angle following the ISO 14801 standard using a dedicated dental testing device (DYNA5dent, DYNA-MESS, Germany). The load level was set to 150 N for all samples. FE models of both designs were created in Abaqus and the durability analysis software fe-safe (SIMULIA, France), replicating the experimental fatigue test and evaluating different load levels. The material and surface properties were taken from a previous study on AM Ti6Al4V [3]. Surface roughness of the scaffold was assessed and considered in the simulations by means of a stress concentration factor [3]. Failure was determined as the number of cycles for which 0.5% of the scaffold's volume failed.

Results

In an ongoing analysis, testing of three samples with the SP design has been accomplished. Failure location predicted by the FE simulation (Fig 1d) corresponded well to the experimentally observed results (Fig 1b). The FE-based fatigue lifetime matched well the experimental results, with the latter showing good reproducibility (Fig 2). The SP design exhibited a

significantly higher fatigue resistance than the SW designs for all load levels of the FE analyses.

Figure 1: a) Fractured 3D-printed porous titanium sample with SP cell geometry; b) Failed sample; c) Corresponding FE model; d) contour plot of the number of cycles to failure ($\log(N_f)$) for a 150 N fatigue load.

Figure 2: Number of cycles to failure versus the fatigue load level for both the Schwarz primitive (SP, green) and the Schwarz W (SW, red) cells geometry designs. Circles: simulations, crosses: experiments.

Discussion

These preliminary results demonstrate the potential of FE models in accurately predicting the fatigue failure of AM porous titanium scaffolds. Once fully validated, the in silico method presented here can be further utilized to investigate further scaffolds designs and customize their properties while ensuring stability.

References

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